

No Naked Singularity, Whatever The Physical Collapse

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Abstract:

After we discussed and confirmed the absence of naked singularities, and over extremality, relying on multi-fold gravity considerations extended to our real universe, a preprint was posted, suggesting scenarios built on a slew of older works, including some non-homogeneous collapses, where singularities could form before an horizon appears, therefore exposing a naked singularity, and violating the Weak Cosmic Censorship Conjecture (WCCC). The singularity would be event-like, as there is no dispute that after a while it would be hidden. The preprint also consider the case of dust with pressurizes as it becomes denser, or equivalent scalar fields, under the right condition, a persistent naked singularity appears.

This paper explains why that is not the case for collapses in a multi-fold universe, where singularities do not appear anyway. The arguments rely on multi-fold black models, which behave differently from conventional black holes within their horizons, and which we have argued to be good candidate for black hole in our real universe as they do not have a black hole information paradox problem. Accordingly, matter does not rush the same way towards the singularity, and can stay sandwiched between the horizon and maximal trapped surfaces/inner horizons, leading to a Russian doll structure. As a result, at no time, do we have a naked singularity.

Then the paper discuss other use cases encountered in the literature: non-spherical dust collapses, also supposed to lead, under the right circumstances, to naked singularities. Again, the black hole Russian doll model, ensures that a future horizon forms from a maximal trapped surface forms, and hides any singularity. Also, black hole disintegration, by reaching (over) extremality are handled.

Therefore, we persist that the WCCC is satisfied with ever possible singularity always hidden by an horizon: the counter example use cases proposed in the literature are unphysical. In multi-fold universes, the same behavior occurs even if no gravitational, nor cosmological, singularity ever appears.

1. Introduction

[189], and references therein, present two scenarios where the collapse of a inhomogeneous dust cloud leads to an event-like naked singularity, in the case that the dust cloud is way denser at its center, just as expected of stellar bodies, or to a future-permanent naked singularity, when pressures are added to the model of collapsed dust clouds, or analogous scalar fields. The use cases had already been investigated [231], for example in [190-195], and in [196-201]. Both cases, but especially the latter are typically modeled in a Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) cosmological model, i.e., an expanding asymptotic de Sitter universe.

[189] focuses on primordial black hole because it relies on scalar fields instead of the dust cloud, and it argues that such fields would have been dominant in the very early universe when primordial black holes, and now, according

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to [189], primordial naked singularities would have formed. Such naked singularities would violate the Weak Cosmic Censorship Conjecture (WCCC) [157,234], a problem in a *stable* universe, which could lead for example to causality violation problems.

In previous papers, we supported the WCCC, and discussed how homogeneous collapse have no naked singularity, nor over extremality, and extended these latter considerations beyond spherical cases [151,157,162]. In our view that settled also the inhomogeneous cases. Now confronted with [189-201], it behooves to us to clarify and explain why the conclusions in [189-201] are unphysical, and our previous arguments hold.

Section 2 will discuss the first scenario of the collapse of an inhomogeneous dust cloud (denser at its center) [189], and the apparition of temporary future naked singularities. We will explain why this is encountered, and then, will argue the unphysicality of the models and what should actually take place.

Our arguments in these sections rely on multi-fold black models [1,8-10,22,64,66,89,131,137,152,162], which behave differently from conventional black holes within their horizons, and which we have argued to be good candidate for black hole in our real universe as they do not have a black hole information paradox problem ([64,66,89,a36] and references therein). Accordingly, collapsed and captured matter does not rush the same way towards the singularity (See [237]), and it can stay sandwiched between the horizon (or its maximally extended trapped surface) and inner horizons/associated maximal trapped surfaces². It leads to black holes with an internal Russian doll structure, key to resolving the black hole information paradox [89,226]. As a result, future horizons, or rather maximal trapped surfaces, actually form within the target black hole, not yet formed, before, or along, the formation of singularity (ies), in models that allow them³, and then grow (outwards) towards its final target radius (and shape), as the collapse progresses, and at no time do we have a naked singularities. Indeed, as we will see in section 4, by definition, horizon depends on the content of the black hole that create the horizon property, and not on the existence of the singularity, or detailed distribution of matter within the black hole. The latter is based on the Birkhoff theorem [228,229], which is essentially always correct, even if it is possibly broken in quantum gravity [223,224], in which case. the corrections would be relevant only very close to the horizon, and indistinguishable for a far observer [227]. On the other hand the singularity depends on the behavior of the collapsed and captured matter (and the background spacetime metric). So, we can have surfaces that cannot let anything escape by the definition of a collapse into a black hole as in [213], based on how much matter is in the region whose boundary is the trapped surface, yet possibly no singularity.

When the collapse is non-homogeneous, e.g., with denser layers in the inner part of the collapsing star as discussed in [189], horizons/a horizon grow/grows even if their/its evolution throughout the collapse varies from the homogeneous case [213].

Section 3 follows by tackling the scenario of a dust cloud, or rather scalar field in [189], collapsing with inner pressures of [189]. [189] argues that, under the right condition, it would be possible that the collapse results into future eternally lasting naked singularity, or singular object, because the subsequent inner pressure would prevent the formation of the horizon. We will explain why such a result can be encountered, and, then, as expected, we will show the problem with the models and their unphysicality. As we will see, the collapsing pressured matter experience a repulsive effect, growing as approaching the future black hole center. It creates a suspension of

² In the paper maximal trapped surface stands for maximally extended trapped surface [215]. While the black hole is being formed, it is also known in the literature, including some of the paper we rely on, as apparent horizon. The target final horizons are also what we call future horizons, or target horizons, in this and other papers.

³ As we will be reminded in section 6, multi-fold blacks holes have no singularities [1,8-10,22,64,66,89,131,137,152,162].

matter that slows down its fall towards the center, recovering a black hole Russian doll inner structure, with enough future horizons that any singularity will never be naked⁴.

In section 4, we will ensure that our notions of singularity and collapse matches what is encountered in the literature. We have already seen above that these matter to physically⁵ invalidate [189] and references therein.

Section 5 goes beyond the originally considered paper[189], and associated earlier work [190-201], to argue that non-spherical collapses [209,210], do not lead to naked singularities in a GR universe either. That is contrary to what is typically presented in the literature, and therefore assumed by most in the Physics community [209,210]. Again, we will justify why such results are obtained with the models used, and explain their unphysicality. Again, it amounts to missing the Russian doll inner structure.

Then, section 6 will review key related aspects of the multi-fold universes, with an overview of the broader theory in appendix A, vs. our real universe.

Eventually, in section 7, we revisit the notion of black hole extremality, and third law of black hole thermodynamics [157]. Again, the literature seems to think that it may be violated, e.g., with charged dust or field collapses. In [157], we showed that it is not the case. In this section, we will show that disintegrating a black hole, formed, or future and being formed, by reaching/forcing over extremality is impossible and it does not expose a naked singularity either.

Therefore, we persist that the WCCC is satisfied. If singularity occur, they are always hidden by an horizon: the counter example use cases proposed in the literature are unphysical. In multi-fold universes, the same behavior occurs even if no gravitational, nor cosmological, singularity ever appears.

Of course, our criteria for unphysicality rely on the models we propose for black holes, and questioning the approach taken by most of the Physics community when it comes to understanding and modeling of the inside of black holes [213]. It is currently impossible to validate with observations what happens inside a black hole horizon. However, [189] argues that some observed astronomical bodies may be naked singularities, and those should be (catastrophically) distinguishable everything else. So it may be possible in the future to falsify of our analysis.

2. Inhomogeneous Collapses

The typical view of collapses is based on spherically symmetric and homogeneous collapses as in the Oppenheimer and Snyder model [151,202]. Inhomogeneous and non-spherically symmetric collapses have been studied, but less often considered in black hole or cosmological discussions [189-201,209,210,231]. Many have heard that they lead to naked singularities, but that other considerations handle the resulting issues and paradoxes, to remediate the impact or preserve the WCCC.

Here we argue that naked singularities simply do not occur in the real universe⁶.

⁴ Indeed these depend only on the matter content they enclose, not that they are regular, singular or with a Russian doll inner structure.

⁵ There is nothing wrong in their mathematical analysis. The problem comes from the models everybody use in the literature for the inside of black holes [189-201,209,210,213].

⁶ It is of course trivial in a multi-fold universe as no gravitational or cosmological singularity exist. Yet, even there, we can see that if singularities had occurred they would never be naked anyway [1,8-10,22,131,137,152,162]. We

2.1 The Inhomogeneous Collapse Scenario of [189]

Let us paraphrase and explain, in our proper ways, what is encountered in [189], based on previous papers like [190-195] and references therein.

Different spherical shells of “matter”⁷, are participating in a collapse, like in the usual homogeneous case of the Oppenheimer-Snyder collapse [202]. Above a certain initial mass, curvature goes to infinite at the center, forming a black hole. In a universe governed by General Relativity (GR), the singularity theorems [152,203], and references therein, then imply that the collapse result into a black holes with a singularity and an horizon. The constraint for the collapse to take place is that the maximal trapped surface, i.e., the future horizon, be external to the region of density under consideration [202,203].

The arguments of [189-195] and references⁸ therein are that if this constraint is satisfied for inner regions, then, in a conventional universe governed by GR, a singularity, would grow way faster⁹ than in the case of an homogenous collapse. That is the gist of the argument of [189-195]. The singularity would form faster [237], while it takes technically an asymptotic infinite time for the horizon to form, but more importantly that time would be longer. So for a while at least the singularity would be naked, i.e., not protected by an horizon, and so, it would be visible to external observers, including ultimately those infinitely far. The naked singularity would be temporary as it would be hidden once the horizon forms.

Such singularities are “not strong” [203], but it does not really matter, as we argue in this paper that they do not physically exist.

Note that the models in [189-195] also inherently consider a de Sitter (dS) expanding universe. It’s been shown that the positive cosmological constant term slows down the collapse of matter, limiting also the size of the black hole [243].

2.2 Naked Singularities and Physics

The implications of naked singularities for Physics are unknown, besides the potential causality violations, with the creation of closed time like curves, the loss of predictability and determinism [232], hyperbolicity [238], loss of unitarity [235,236], and instability problems that would probably result [230,231,237]. It is argued that in the case of the present scenarios, as well as in the case of the ones in section 3, matter involved in the collapse could reduce such visibility of the singularity¹⁰, potentially resolving the concerns, albeit we do not know for sure what it means

assert that this analysis can be repeated in the real universe, where singularities have not been rules out, to the contrary [213,214,237], unless if it was discrete [244], something that we believe to also be the case as in [1,6,8-10,16,23,27,29,32,36,53,59,62,68,72,112,131,137,142,148,150,152,155,161, 169,170,174-177,179,181] and references therein.

⁷ Dust clouds, or scalar field regions behaving like dust cloud per [189].

⁸ Many more papers have bene published on the topic.

⁹ Consider two homogeneous regions. An large outer crust and a denser core. It is assumed, and modeled, that the singularity would appear faster than if we had an homogeneous collapse of a sphere of the density of the outer shell, because it forms first and foremost from the denser (and closer to the center) core.

¹⁰ Or even fully hide it, further in the cloud or outside the cloud.

for the local matter that can see or feel it. Reasonings as in [162,177,181], and references therein, would indicate that a Bose Einstein Condensate (BEC) could appear.

[189] and references therein argue that we do not know if such collapses and situations exist, but it presents a list already observed candidates¹¹ of naked singularities. The observational signatures of naked singularities differ significantly from those of black holes [238-240]. While black holes always cast shadows due to their event horizons, naked singularities may or may not produce shadows depending on their specific structure [237,238]. Naked singularities without photon spheres produce distinctive "full-moon" images instead of shadows [237]. This occurs because light rays can approach arbitrarily close to the singularity and still escape to infinity, resulting in a bright central region rather than a dark shadow [237,239].

2.3. Analysis

2.3.1 There Is Actually No Naked Singularity

Part of the problems with [189-195], are that conventional General Relativity (GR) black holes, like the Schwarzschild black hole [212,213], rely on a simple, not necessarily a correct, or physical, model of the "outside", and also assuming to correctly model the inside¹². Assumption are typically based on changes of variables, which remove some misbehaviors near the horizon, and analytic continuation of the external metric [213]. Because of the black hole horizons, even if future, or rather the maximal trapped surfaces involved in the collapses, we have no way to know how appropriate, and physically correct, the internal modeling is. Internal models rely on analytic extensions, changes of variable and (wild) interpretation of the resulting new coordinate. It's elegant, but unverified.

And yes, [189-195,213,237] provide GR solutions.

According to these models, in the proper time of an observer falling into the Schwarzschild black hole, once inside, it takes a finite time to reach the center, where the singularity forms. The collapse period is just an early stage that starts to approximate such behavior that always end up with a singularity per the GR singularity theorem [203]. Charged and rotating black holes have to be treated differently [2,3], but it does not change the argument.

Assuming that the Oppenheimer-Snyder collapse [202] is a correct model for spherically symmetric homogeneous matter, then the inhomogeneous scenario can be well approximated by:

- a denser homogeneous collapse on the inner side, i.e., the core, and
- a subsequent external lower density homogeneous collapse with an external density.

Following [202], in GR, a singularity will eventually appear, per the singularity theorems [203]. But a trapped surface and horizon will also appear at the same time for the inner core. The rest collapses towards it, and will take \sim forever to cross the inner trapped surface / future horizon, as it becomes an horizon and grows in radius as we evolve towards future infinity, while it captures the external content¹³. Therefore, just as [203] does not allow for a naked singularity, the inhomogeneous case also does not introduces naked singularities.

¹¹ The analysis of the present paper implies that other explanations is needed for these proposed scenarios.

¹² At best just based on (analytic) continuity of the "equations" [213]

¹³ Consider figure 1(a) with an overall spherical shape, instead of egg shaped, and the inner core being denser.

Corner cases, as considered in [189-195,237,243] exist, but they amount to situations where no horizon and no singularity form. They are not problematic: no black hole would ever appear and no singularity forms. In fact the collapse will probably settle towards other stellar bodies like for example a neutron star and/or possibly a (super)nova. Again, no naked singularity, the WCCC is preserved.

2.3.2. What Went Wrong With [189-195,237], And Conventional GR Black Hole Physics?

Obviously, we are not suggesting mathematical or simulation mistakes in [189-195,237], and related work encountered in the literature.

The problem is that the scenarios explored in [189-195,237] rely on an ansatz of a working metric that can be interpreted as associated to an inhomogeneous density distribution. But they did not consider that:

- such inhomogeneous scenarios need to be modeled with a set of at least 2 collapse structures as Russian dolls.
- such an ansatz is postulated, and accepted because of behaving well, but not derived from other models/equations, other than for example the Lemaître–Tolman–Bondi metric, again metrics for the external region, not the inside of the black hole, and it misses the ability to account for our proposed Russian doll structure; another ansatz would have had to be postulated instead for that. These choices are arbitrary as long as they are solutions of GR.

This is why we dare to assert that the analyses of [189-195,213,231,237] are unphysical. They just do not represent what is physically happening.

[189-195,237] have found GR solutions. We do not know if they correspond to a stable universe, or are related to any other physical use cases, but based on our analysis above they do not correspond to the inhomogeneous dust/scalar field collapses targeted by [189-195,237], including in primordial black hole scenarios, where dust would be replaced by scalar fields [189].

And so when updating the ansatz or models, no physical naked singularity scenario is encountered any more. We also suspect that dS expanding spacetimes and the Lemaître–Tolman–Bondi metrics, and their ability to stop collapse and even singularities [243], may have also comforted the Physics community that all their ansatz and models make sense.

2.4 Wilder Inhomogeneous Distributions

So far in this discussion, we focused on an initial distribution where the denser matter is towards the center of the collapsing object. Of course other distributions could be envisaged, even if harder to justify physically. Consider for example a structure where the density decreases when we get closer to its center, just the opposite of the models so far.

In the case of a simultaneous shell collapse (dust), we have:

$$\Delta t_i(r) = \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{R_i(r)^3}{2GM(r)}} \quad (1)$$

Based on the Lemaître–Tolman–Bondi metric, which is a non-homogeneous isometric metric solution of GR, close correspondent to the Schwarzschild metric for homogeneous cases [241,242]. It models also dust without pressure. Accordingly [237], the total time it takes for a spherical shell of dust, labeled by a coordinate r , to collapse from its initial state to a central singularity of infinite density where its radius becomes zero is $\Delta t_i(r)$, where $R_i(r)$ is the physical radius of the dust shell r at the initial time¹⁴. $M(r)$ is the total mass-energy enclosed within the initial radius $R_i(r)$. It is determined by the initial density profile $\rho_i(r)$ of the dust cloud. The more mass enclosed within a shell, the stronger the gravitational pull that it experiences (*).

On the basis of (1), and extending the principle of (1) to core sphere vs. shell as still roughly valid when we have no pressure, we see that in, typical GR models, higher density shell more external to lower density ones may catch up, and cross then pass the lower density shells (at least logically). It turns out that this is observed with models [189,196-201] and known as shell crossing¹⁵. It can lead to unimportant singularities, reported in [189,196-201], for the equations just as the coordinate singularities for say Schwarzschild black hole / metric, a well-known situation, of no particular interest.

However, (1), and its obvious physical interpretation (*), also imply that, in such GR models, a denser external shell in collapse catches up with lower density ones. It would bring us ultimately to either a more homogeneous collapse or the case of 2.1. Therefore, we already know that there are no naked singularity, as we encounter situations which are ultimately equivalent.

2.5 No Naked Singularity In Spherically Symmetric Inhomogeneous Collapses

Our conclusions at this stage, is that, we encounter no naked singularity In spherically symmetric inhomogeneous collapses. It is because we have black holes which have Russian doll inner structures, recovering the structure of multi-fold black holes [89].

3. Pressurized Collapses (In An Asymptotic dS Universe)

As in [189,196-201], pressurized collapses are collapses where inner pressure appears during the collapse as the matter (dust or scalar field) density increases. These are more realistic scenarios for dust collapses than those considered in section 2.

3.1 The Collapse Scenario

¹⁴ And yes, (1) is not valid in our models with the Russian doll structure.

¹⁵ Physically, shell crossing may mix their content or homogenize the densities, instead of staying different shells, which is another limitation of the Lemaître–Tolman–Bondi metric to model such dust collapses.

[189,196-201], model collapses where the collapsing matter, i.e., dust cloud, fluid or scalar field, creates pressure as it collapses. It results into further inhomogeneities within the matter distribution.

The analysis of [189] is done in a Friedmann-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) cosmological model, i.e., an expanding asymptotic de Sitter (dS) universe. It may matter for their models [243], but it really does not matter for the analyses that we provide, other than the fact that we know that our real universe is strictly dS, i.e., expanding with a strictly positive constant [1,8-10,22,112,131,137,144,152,170,181].

[189,196-201] focuses on tangential pressure effects, as encountered through the stress tensor in continuum mechanics and fluid mechanics [a26-a29], but one could also consider radial contributions. Rather than resulting in shear forces, they result into radially repulsive effects within the collapsing matter.

3.1.1 Radial pressure

The radial pressure is analogous to the effect of a charged black holes on charged particles [2], and also in analogy with rotating black holes [3,187].

As a result, if a radial pressure appears¹⁶ in the black hole or during collapse, the maximal trapped surface / future horizon radius decreases for a same mass vs. the Schwarzschild case. Therefore, the maximal trapped surface could even reach the singularities. In such case, we could have future eternal/long lasting naked singularities. Otherwise, at lower pressure, we have pressured black hole with singularities and horizon. Consider the analysis in [157], especially Appendix B1, re-purposed for this situation.

If the radial pressure, set by parameters of the model, is too high, then no black hole forms, or the black hole formation disintegrate just as for charged or rotating (over) extremal black holes as explored in [157] and references therein. It corresponds to when the singularity would meet the inner horizon in the literature. Such cases do not lead to naked singularities. Additional aspects are discussed in section 7.

3.1.2 Tangential pressure

Let us now consider the case of a tangential pressure as is actually considered in [189], as in continuum or fluid mechanics: the compression from the gravity presses matter as dust particles against each other. This increases everywhere the tangential pressure (and stress). If matter were incompressible, and unbreakable it would stop moving towards the singularity (at least for a while), and/or bulk outwards, e.g., because of the spherical curvature of the mater shell under consideration, and its unstable state, a typical buckling scenario [225]. Alternatively, it

¹⁶ We will not argue here if such a non-negligible radial pressure could naturally exist as all particles would move attracted slightly more on the inside layer than the outside layer in a 3 layers snapshot of dust/particles. As the inner layer is attracted more than the middle one, itself less than the other one, the middle layer is not more pressurized by being pushed against the inner or outer layers. So, one would need to understand where, when and how radial pressure would appear. On the other hand, tangential pressure within a layer seems to be potentially more naturally occurring; there is simply nowhere else to go as the shell contracts as it moves towards the singularity.

could disintegrate until reaching a mix of just fundamental particles, or change phase to accommodate the effects¹⁷.

In the former case of the previous paragraph, if enough matter already “got close to the center” to form an inner horizon/maximal trapped surface, then that part may form a future, black hole and potentially compel everything else outside and close enough to eventually fall into it. In a conventional GR universe we may¹⁸ have a singularity. The effect of the repulsion created by the overall outward bulking instabilities is equivalent to the charge repulsion in a charged black hole [157,213]. It is everywhere and increasing towards the center. As a result, the maximal trapped surface / future horizon retreats towards the center and may end up reaching the center, giving this impression that it would allow long lasting naked singularities as in [189,196-201].

3.2. Analysis

3.2.1 There Is Actually No Naked Singularity

However, continuing the latter case detailed in the previous paragraph, having a maximal trapped surface retreat towards the center doesn't lead to a naked singularities. That is because of the formation of internal trapped surface(s) / future horizon(s), that depends on the total matter it contains, not its distribution, per the Birkhoff theorem [228,229], valid with GR and roughly valid (except very close to the horizons) for quantum gravity. Models like [189,196-201] simply miss this option, only considering that matter falls straight to the center, because of the mathematical details captured in (1). Instead, we have at least one, but in reality a multitude of trapped surface forming, keeping the falling matter in slowed down suspension. All do not retreat. So, we encounter the Russian doll structure of multi-fold black holes [1,8-10,22,89,131,137,152]. We have no naked singularity.

On the other hand, if not enough matter exists inside the region ,where excessive tangential pressure appears, to justify the formation of future horizons, then no trapped surface, or future black hole, will appear, but then, of course, no singularity will appear either. Hence no naked singularity. Indeed, we do not have a sustained increase of matter near the center to justify and increase to infinity of the curvature, as internally this can be seen as behaving like the Oppenheimer Snyder [213], which gets infinite curvature only when enough mass is involved.

In the latter case of the first paragraph of section 3.1.2, our previous work indicates that we should end-up with a BEC of fundamental elementary particles, as encountered in [114] and references therein, and endorsed in [162,177,181], and references therein, including [205-208]. As argued in [162,177,181], this would spatially distribute the gravitational attraction (and pressure). Singularities probably do not exist, i.e., we have a regular / non-singular black hole as discussed in [162,204]. With the change of phase (possible at the end of decomposition), the blocking effect due to tangential pressure goes away, e.g., as in BEC, or reduces, and a black hole horizon can form, but it is regular. Again, we have no naked singularity.

So, a few considerations can be added to the list. If horizons / trapped surfaces can't form, it would be because the collapse is stalled. And if the collapse is stalled then:

- No new singularity will form, and an horizon may or may not form (regular vs. singular black hole).

¹⁷ A good example would be the transformation into a BEC mentioned earlier and discussed in related scenarios in [162,177,181] and references therein.

¹⁸ The black hole may also be non-singular, or regular, as discussed in [162,204] and references therein.

- If a singularity has already formed, then matter will ultimately be crushed and pulled in, crushed into fundamental particles eventually reached by these particles, but way slower than (1) because of the Russian doll structure. Singularities will form, as will horizon, business as usual.
- As the amount of matter captured increases the horizon/trapped surface radius, if one exists, grows away from the singularities.

In any case, no naked singularity appears.

3.2.2. What Went Wrong With [189,196-201], and Conventional GR Black Hole Physics?

The problem is that the models [189,196-201] rely proposed ansatz, and again with the Lemaître–Tolman–Bondi metric which seems to evolve to intuitively model a collapse with (tangential) pressure [189,196-201,237,241,242]. This again will result into what the ansatz can model, not necessarily what physically happens, even if the ansatz can be a solution of GR. It is not different from section 2.

In the present case, the ansatz has the built-in formation of the singularity, and only models well the stalled collapse / horizon formation and growth. Just as for charged black holes multiple maximal trapped surfaces / future horizon can form, and not all retreat. On the other hand, the formation of a singularity may or may not occur [162]. If enough matter was already present, then an inner horizon exists, and we have non naked singularity.. If nor, well then no naked singularity anyway.

Again a suitable Russian doll model for the black hole/collapse should have rather been used to model the Physics of such a collapse.

Interestingly, multi-fold black holes have exactly this Russian doll structure [89], as discussed in section 6.

4. About Horizons & Singularities

Let us make sure that we have definitions of horizons and singularities that match conventional Physics.

4.1 Conventional Horizons

Our definition of horizon is relatively straightforward. Most commonly, it indicates the boundary of a region from which no particles (of any type, or only of certain type like neutral/what type of charge, or what direction of spin) can escape, i.e., cross in a specific (set of) spacetime direction(s).

We do not explicitly need to introduce the notion of Cauchy horizon [211], that would then become a physical surface that no particle (of any, or of a certain type) can cross unscathed¹⁹ in a specific spacetime direction. This is based on the analysis in [157]. In the cases of charged or rotating black holes, both have an internal horizon unstable with respect to quantum fluctuations²⁰, leading to the cryptographic censorship conjecture [151,212] (and references therein) and mass inflation [151,213] (and references therein). This is how to explain that the internal horizons are Cauchy horizons.

With this model, horizons are directly function of the mass (and charge or spin) distribution within the black hole, or enclosed by the surface, depending on the scenario.

During the initial collapse, the future horizon is essentially the limit of the maximal trapped surface, aka what is often known as the apparent horizon [215].

4.2 Conventional Singularities

Here, we speak only of conventional singularities as there are no gravitational or cosmological singularities in a multi-fold universe [1,8-10,22,64,66,89,131,137,152,157,162,181].

4.2.1 Definitions and Criteria for Singularities

The following are the different kind of black hole singularities and their properties encountered in conventional Physics.

4.2.1.1 In General Relativity

In general relativity, a singularity is typically defined as a region where certain physical quantities (such as curvature invariants) become infinite, or more rigorously, where spacetime is geodesically incomplete. It means that there exist paths (geodesics) that cannot be extended in a smooth way, indicating a breakdown of the spacetime manifold.

¹⁹ By this, we mean that the particle do not have a suitable future causally depending of the past history(ies) / initial conditions. It is typically named as a Cauchy surface, with time-like geodesic on one side, and spacelike geodesic on the other [211].

²⁰ Creation of charges pairs (or non-zero spin pairs) result into large fluctuations of (/ UV effects on) the inner horizon position, creating these effects, and potentially erasing (e.g., chaotically confusing them) histories/causality (due to charge change affecting the position of the horizon (or spin impact like with dynamic/frame dragging [115] effects as in [157])). We note that it is another example where GR, without the knowledge of QFT/particle physics and creation/annihilation of particles, manages to model these implications through other facets, namely the loss of causality, instabilities and the possible apparition of problematic closed time like loops. We have also encountered this often when it came to GR, or Quantum Physics, and Multi-fold aspects.

The most widely accepted conventional criterion for a singularity is geodesic incompleteness, as formalized in the Hawking-Penrose singularity theorems ([151,203] and references therein). This approach avoids coordinate-dependent definitions, and focuses on the inability to extend geodesics, which are the paths followed by free-falling particles or light.

While many singularities are associated with diverging curvature, such as the Kretschmann scalar becoming infinite, not all incomplete geodesics are accompanied by such divergences, and vice versa.

Note recent works showing that this behavior in GR, is not restricted to the smooth manifolds resulting from differential calculus, but may also appear in way worse behaving manifolds. A review and compilation of recent results can be found at [245].

4.2.1.2 In Black Holes

Black Hole Singularities

In the context of black holes, singularities are predicted to form at the center (e.g., the Schwarzschild singularity), where the curvature of spacetime becomes infinite [202,203,213]. These are hidden behind event horizons, making them inaccessible to external observers.

There are exceptions: regular / non-singular black holes, including multi-fold black holes, as discussed in [1,8-10,22,64,66,89,131,137,152,157,162,181,204]. Multi-fold black holes are revisited in section 6.

Collapses

Penrose's theorem demonstrates that, under general conditions (such as the existence of a trapped surface and the weak energy condition), singularities are a generic outcome of gravitational collapse, independent of symmetry assumptions ([151,203] and references therein).

4.2.1.3 Quantum Gravity

Among other things, quantum gravity, which we know to be the nature of gravity [146], is expected to resolve classical singularities [a31]. For example, loop quantum gravity (LQG) suggests that quantum effects can eliminate singularities like the Big Bang or black hole singularities, replacing them with a quantum bounce or regular core [a32]. Unconventionally, but aligned, as discussed in section 6, multi-fold universe have no gravitational, or cosmological, singularities.

As discussed in the references in [151,162,221], quantum gravity can account for regular, i.e., non-singular black holes, even without exotic matter (conventionally by involving higher order gravity terms). This is a significant step towards understanding how quantum effects might resolve the singularities predicted by general relativity, just as they might invalidate the Birkhoff theorem [223,224]. Note that this is a different direction from [245], where non-smoothness of manifolds does not mean a quantum model, even if potentially motivated by say quantum foam [246]. Idem for [247,248] in the semi classical case.

4.3 Applying The Above To The previous Scenarios

In this section, we relate the physical considerations of the scenarios of sections 2 and 3 with these definitions of horizons and singularities, and confirm our results from these previous sections.

4.3.1 The Scenario of Section 2

The Russian doll black hole structure that we argue for in [89] and in section 2, implies combined collapses with enough mass (at least down to a certain radius) due to the higher density in the center to start form a hierarchical set of black holes embedded within each other's (and each contributing to the more external horizons). This can be modeled by the Oppenheimer and Snyder collapse [202], which implies an exponentially growing curvature, i.e., a singularity, and yes, that means convergence of all light geodesics, which will end in a future + finite²¹ time.

Meanwhile, (inner or outer) horizons form based on the amount of matter within the maximal corresponding trapped surface (or in the full black hole when considering charged or rotating black holes), once enough is involved. Effects of massless gravity propagate at the speed of light. As a result the horizon or maximal trapped surface always occur before the singularity can be seen outside that horizon. It holds for all these regular collapses. As discussed in section 2, it happens for corresponding inhomogeneous collapse. There is no concept of a singularity occurring first, without an (inner) horizon, or maximal trapped surface, for that dense region occurring at the same time. These are future effects, it takes a while to have the singularity, future formed. That time is always the same, or longer than the time of a corresponding horizon to form, and prevent any particle to leak out. Indeed the latter depends solely on massless and massive particle (possibly with certain properties) not being able to escape. The Russian doll structure delays even further the formation of the singularity, and ensure "many" maximal horizons or future horizons hiding it, like a Mille-feuille.

4.3.2 The Scenario of Section 3

In the presence of pressure within the collapsing dust or scalar field, we focused on tangential, as generic/radial considerations and BEC have been discussed already in [151,157,162] and references therein, and as we saw that radial pressure is not what [189] focuses on, and in fact may not systematically be occurring (See earlier footnote 16). As we saw, in section 3, falling matter moves towards the central region are slowed down.

In terms of singularities, the future singularity formation are slowed down, while the (outer) horizon depends only on the matter within it.

²¹ It is a bit a tongue in cheek arguments as formation of the black hole takes an infinite amount of time. But the point is that, when close enough to be like a black hole, these effects occur and, in the present case, light geodesic terminate in a finite amount of time, hence singularities occur.

It again shows that horizons will not form later than the singularity. It is even more clear cut than in the scenario of an homogeneous collapse or the scenarios of section 2, because the tangential pressure also lead conventionally to aspects mimicking Russian dolls²², with inner and outer horizons.

5. Non-Spherical Collapse

Figure 1: (a) Illustrates a non-spherically symmetric distribution of matter that could collapse. It can be a dust cloud, its scalar equivalent, with or without inner pressure during the collapse. (b) shows how it could be modeled as a symmetric collapse, that then also captures additional matter. Multiple such spherical collapses can coexist.

Non-spherical collapses have also been considered in the literature [209,210], typically with numerical GR [214], and some models with some closed form approximations. According to the literature, naked singularities appear during such collapses [209,210].

As for the inhomogeneous collapses, we argue that it is not the case, again because the models used for the numerical simulation, or approximations behind the numerical computations, are ansatz / models built just like the spherically symmetric models for Schwarzschild, charged and / or rotating black holes [2,3,213]. They carry assumptions that they work outside the black hole but may not be physical inside the black hole.

Let us explain why they can be wrong.

Consider figure 1(a), where the density and pressure could also be modeled. In this paper, and the following figures, we do not discuss the additional effect of pressure or inhomogeneity. They can be handled as in sections 2 to 4, adapted to this discussion.

Figure 1(b) shows a non-spherically symmetric collapse as the sum of the largest possible spherically symmetric black holes, and one or multiple extra matter distributions being captured in parallel by these spherical black holes in collapse, and formation. Multiple such symmetric collapses can coexist. We can essentially consider three classes of scenarios:

- black hole(s) merger,
- matter captured by blackholes,

²² Except that the models in [a0,a7-a12] focused on thinking that the horizon formation is slowed down, instead of rather seeing it as slowing down only the singularity formation.

- and non-blackhole matter clumping.

Let us consider each scenario.

5.1 Black Hole Merger Scenario

In this case, illustrated in figure 2, the collapse can be modeled as a merger of two²³ (future) black holes, i.e., 2 collapsing symmetrical black holes, along with some additional matter capture that represent the differences with this approximate merger model.

Figure 2. It illustrates a collapse of the matter in figure 1 (a), which can be seen as a dominant merger (red deformation of the spherical horizons per [157] and references therein) of multiple collapses into multiple spherically symmetric black holes, and some extra matter capture (dark blue arrows).

All these steps occur in parallel.

As we know, spherically symmetric collapses conventionally²⁴ result into future black holes without naked singularities and with horizons.

High level considerations on black hole mergers and references, including to numerical models, are discussed in [157,214]. Accordingly, the main (dominant) merger implies that the horizons, which we take as the corresponding maximum trapped surfaces, deform but remain future²⁵ horizons/maximal trapped surfaces from which lights and other particles can't escape (easily till full horizons) anymore. Lost conserved quantities, like energy or angular momentum, are carried out by the associated gravitational waves [157] and references therein. Nothing else escapes, no singularity becomes naked. In [157] we discussed that this does not "break" the black holes like due to over extremalities in the process, a notion revisited in section 7, where we see that even that will have no lead to naked singularities anyway, and therefore, in particular, it does not destroy the existing horizons, even as they are being formed from the maximal trapped surfaces.

The additional corrections correspond to additional matter not yet accounted for and can be seen as extra gravitational capture by black holes.

²³ More black holes could be involved, but they amount to a repeat of the reasoning with two black holes.

²⁴ Qualified because regular and multi-fold black holes are alternatives. In any cases they would also be without naked singularities.

²⁵ All black holes are physically future, so [157] applies.

In such a scenario there is no naked singularity. It is not representative of the values in the models represented in in figure 1 of [209].

It is not hard to repeat the analysis of sections 2 to 4 to extend the result to inhomogeneous and/or pressurized non-spherical collapse matching this scenario. The Russian doll structure will actually appear initially, and maybe ironically, with shapes very similar to actual Russian dolls.

5.2 Black Hole Capture Of Extra Matter

Figure 3 illustrates the case where the matter collapse amounts to a spherically symmetric collapse, and extra matter capture. This collapse applies to figure 1(b) for example.

In this case, illustrated in figure 3, matter is captured by a black hole business as usual. New matter implies a growth of the outside horizon. The future horizon, or maximal trapped surface (apparent horizon) grows as more content is absorbed. However, there are other effects: the gravity of the excentric matter, at the far away pole, fights against the collapse, attracting matter near, and at / inside the near the original horizon / maximal trapped surface of the dominant spherical black hole. This pushes the future horizon / trapped surface inward, as more gravity effects are needed to counter these effects, all other things remaining the same, as shown in figure 4(a).

As a result we can understand why incorrect models can provide behaviors as in figures 1 and 2 of [209], and as in [210] with its related figures. These papers use models and ansatz that are missing the possibilities of black holes with Russian doll structure. They miss that the inner horizon/maximal trapped surface of the dominant black hole will form within the largest region, along with a future singularity at its center (i.e., shifted from the center of the overall matter). This is illustrated in figure 4(a). Just as for pressurized matter, as it collapses, or charged black holes, as discussed earlier, the maximal trapped surface, nearest to that pole, including the whole collapsing matter now curves and moves inwards (as shown / simulated in [209,210]), leading to an inward convex shape near the far away pole²⁶ as in figure 1 in [209].

²⁶ This is assuming homogeneous collapse.

Figure 4. It illustrates the effects of the captured matter on the inner black hole horizon. Because also it attracts the matter from the black hole, the maximal internal spherically symmetric trapped surface of the original dominant black hole is curved inwards, in a convex manner, by the gravity effects of the external matter. As the rest of matter is captured, the maximal trapped surface grows and this effects starts acting the other way. It corrects the distribution of mass within the black hole, with a Russian doll structure, ending up eventually close to a spherical collapse.

As the bulging matter is captured, the trapped surface and horizon will grow, and push²⁷ against the convex shape towards a future larger (closer to a rough sphere as) maximal trapped surface/horizon. Indeed captures mass adds to the ass suspended in the Russian doll structure. The mass distribution becomes more spherically symmetric. That is a latter stage not represented in versus figure 1 in [209].

So figure 1 in [209] is an interim good approximation, but it does not lead to the horizon meeting the singularity, or breaking open as accumulated captured mass stays in suspension (Russian doll structure) as discussed in previous sections and in [1,8-10,22,89,131,137,152], and pushes the trapped surface outwards, compensating the inward convex curvature trend. The horizon does not reach the singularity, and therefore, there is no naked singularity. Also it does not open. The effects do not break the horizon, as this does not happen for a spherically symmetric black hole. BH1 is a future spherically symmetric black hole.

As we can see, the main difference between our figure 4, and figure 1 in [209], which is the typical literature view for naked singularities in non-spherical collapses, is that the latter again misses the fact that we have internal future horizons/maximal trapped surface, which grows instead of solely approaching the singularity. This prevents the trapped surface to reach the singularity. Again, the Russian doll structures makes all the difference²⁸.

With this we have no naked singularity in such a collapse. Again the same analysis can be repeated with inhomogeneous collapses or collapses with inner pressure.

Now if no horizon forms in the dominant region, we are in the case of the next sub-section.

5.3 Blobs Of Matter Clumping

²⁷ In the Russian doll model, matter stays longer in suspension.

²⁸ Indeed in the case of figure 1 in [2103.07190v2.pdf], the matter goes rapidly to the singularity instead of in quasi suspension in the Russian doll structure. This explains why that figure lets the horizon reach the singularity, and the ,maximal trapped surface could ed up being open. But it is not what happens as we discussed here.

In this case, illustrated in figure 5. We have no singularity or horizon until / if enough matter appears to trigger a collapse into a black hole. The collapse stops before encountering a region of infinite curvature²⁹, and no black hole forms, until, and unless, due to other effects like rotation, the matter redistributes so that eventually a region start that to behave as a black hole and we are back to one of the two scenarios above, in the previous two subsections.

Asteroid in our solar systems are good examples.

Figure 5. No collapse takes place after a while, with the current amount of clumped matter. Locally, everywhere, the collapse stops with finite curvature. Otherwise we would have encountered one of the scenarios of figure 2 to 4.

This can also be encountered if the matter is also inhomogeneous, or pressurized as it collapses.

5.4 Putting It All Together

Combining and being able to smoothly evolve from one scenario to another covers all possible cases, and variations. Under no circumstance do we ever encounter naked singularities.

6. In A Multi-fold Universe, No Gravitational or Cosmological Singularity

An overview and references to the multi-fold theory are provided in Appendix A.

6.1 No singularity

²⁹ Otherwise we would be in one of the previous scenarios.

In a multi-fold universe we have no cosmological or gravitational singularities [1,8-10,22,131,137,152,162]. Singularities simply do not occur because of effects like:

- Discrete spacetime [1,6,8-10,16,23,27,29,32,36,53,59,62,68,72,112,131,137,142,148,150,152,155,161,169,170,174-177,179,181].
 - Interestingly, conventional models of GR dust collapse, also recover both signs that spacetime is discrete, with another hint that this is indeed the case, but also confirm that Planck size discreteness ensures no singularity [244], confirming a key multi-fold result.
- (Related) Non-commutative effects [1,6,8-10,16,23,27,29,32,36,53,59,62,68,72,112,131,137,142,148,150,152,155,161,169,170,174-177,179,181]
- (Related or complementary) multi-fold dark energy effects³⁰ [1,8-10,22,27,131,137,152,181]
- Possible torsion effects [1,8-10,22,131,137,152].
- Fractal spacetime and 2D random walks of massless Higgs bosons [1,8-10,22,70,72,131,137,152,162,176,177,181]
- (Related) Primordial BEC [1,8-10,22,131,137,152,162,177,181], which also erases any big bang singularity, spreading out the effects.

Regular, i.e., non-singular black holes, initially inspired from Bardeen [204], are discussed in [162] and references therein.

So, in a multi-fold universe, the WCCC is automatically satisfied and there are no naked singularities. However, multi-fold black holes have the properties (regular and with a Russian doll structure), argued for in the present paper to make sense and satisfy the WCCC.

6.2 Multi-fold black holes

[1,8-10,22,89,131,137,151,152,162] provide for a Russian doll model of black hole horizons, without singularities. In particular, it seems to address the black hole information paradox [89,a36], and account for quantum extremal surfaces also encountered via the replica trick [64,66,89].

Throughout our work on the multi-fold theory [1-188], we have time and time again observed that:

- The multi-fold model can provide compelling (partial) justifications for observations in, or properties of, the real universe.
- The multi-fold theory can partially, and usually at least qualitatively, address open questions with the standard model (SM) and the standard cosmological model (and its possible recent need to evolve) [100,128]³¹.
- Conventional models like GR, quantum mechanics and QFT, only provide facets of aspects that these theories can't better described, while these aspects are native to the multi-fold theory.

So, without claiming that our real universe is multi-fold, it seems to be well modeled, at times at least, as a multi-fold universe [1-188].

³⁰ This does not mean that dark energy effects result from black hole behavior as discussed in [114,162].

³¹ Including comments at the web page version of the paper [128].

6.3 Multi-fold Black Holes Are Russian Dolls Structures

[89] details the Russian doll structure of multi-fold black holes, needed, expected, or resulting from sections 2 to 4 to salvage the WCCC, and ensure physicality of the collapse scenarios, even if such structures aren't actually needed to satisfy the WCCC in multi-fold universe as no singularities exist anyway.

It seems another example of multi-fold universe capturing subtle features of the real universe and explaining them, as mentioned in section 6.2.

7. Extremality Is Not Loophole To Expose Naked Singularities

Bringing a black hole to (over) extremality, violating the third law of black hole thermodynamics, is not an option as discussed in [157,162]. So, disintegrating the black hole, and hoping for race conditions to expose the singularities of the black hole is never a Physically possible option.

Of course, one could argue that the unphysicality of reaching extremality, and beyond, applies to already formed black holes, maybe not to black holes that are future to a collapse. But it does apply. Indeed consider a black hole in formation.

- If the future black hole is charged à la Reissner–Nordström [2,213], then if over extremal, the static repulsion destroys the black hole while it is being formed. Adding a charged particle repulsion frees all the charged particle in the outer horizon / maximal trapped surface [157], while the inner horizon / maximal trapped surface starts growing, but is still present for a while. See Appendix B1 in [157] for details of the charged black hole horizon. The black hole will then disappear, or evolve to become neutral.
- The reasoning is the same with rotating black holes
- The same applies to charged and rotated black holes

In all these cases, singularities are not left naked.

As we saw earlier in this paper, pressurized collapses support similar reasoning. A(n) set of inner trapped surfaces(/surface) appear(s) due to the additional inner pressure (bulking instability) effects that amounts to a repulsion³², in addition to the outer trapped surface as for a Oppenheimer Snyder collapse as in [202], where pressure is lower³³. However, extremality is not equivalent to the charged case. Indeed disintegration of the future black hole, i.e., halt of the collapse would now be due to too high inner pressures, i.e., as dictated by pressure parameters in the models. Just as in section 3, if the pressure increases too much, e.g., by now adding material / field which generate higher pressures, the inner horizon will reach the future singularity, and the collapse will be “reverted”. No singularity forms and therefore no naked singularity is ever encountered. Remember the if it just involves one inner horizon, as a first approximation, the effect is analogous to a failed Oppenheimer and Snyder collapse, and, therefore, without singularity at the end. No naked singularity result.

³² It resists attraction towards the singularity, or target center of gravity, just as the electromagnetic repulsion between charges occur at the outer horizon for a charged black hole [157,213].

³³ And we again have a Russian doll structure for that reason, leading to horizons for different pressures.

8. No Loopholes?

[151] discussed also (figure 2 in [152]), why and how background spacetime / vacuum and its fluctuations cannot create naked singularities, as they will always be accompanied with the creation of a black hole with an horizon that hides it. And in a multi-fold universe, per section 6, singularities never forms per section 6, as also conventionally encountered for example in [244], if the spacetime is discrete, which we know it is, and claim to also be the case for the real universe [1,6,8-10,16,23,27,29,32,36,53,59,62,68,72,112,131,137,142,148,150,152,155,161, 169,170,174-177,179,181].

9. Conclusions

In this paper, we have extended [1,8-10,22,89,131,137,152,162,177,181], and shown ensured that inhomogeneous or pressurized collapses do not introduce naked singularities in stable universes, rejecting the models of [189-201,237], and, again, we salvaged the WCCC. We did it based on physical microscopic interpretation of what happens within a black hole, rendering the models [189-201,237] unphysical, while remaining consistent with acceptable “definitions” of singularities and horizons.

Then, we showed that previous assumptions on non-spherically symmetric collapses are similarly incorrect: they do not lead to naked singularities either, for very similar reasons.

The microscopic interpretation, and the subsequent Russian doll model for black hole is inspired from multi-fold black holes [89], where, ironically maybe, no gravitational or cosmological singularity exists. It really result from approaching GR and Quantum gravity from a particle point of view in addition to fields. It is a key aspect of the multi-fold theory [1,8-10,22,86,131,137,152]. We see this as salvaging Physics from all the problems that could appear if naked singularities were possible. So far, Physicists either accepted their existence without panicking, claiming even that they may have already been observed, or hoped to hide them within the mess of the collapsing matter. None of these were satisfactory. In a view, a model that preserves the WCCC, and justifies, should have the upper hand over any other approach.

It led to some important lessons. In our universe, black holes seem better modeled as Russian doll structures like for the multi-fold black holes. This is another example where multi-fold models seem to point out, explain or well model aspects of our real universe. Many more examples can be found in [1-188]. In addition, we see that GR models, like numerical seeds, and ansatz, like the metrics to model black holes and collapses [2,3,212,213], may not be the best suited for modeling what really happens within a black hole horizon (and maximal trapped surface).

With respect to [189], frankly it does not matter that we consider primordial singularities or others, they don't exist anyway.

Our conclusions are straightforward: nonspherical, non-homogeneous, and pressurized collapses should never produce any naked singularity.

Appendix A. A Superficial Overview of the Multi-fold Theory

In a multi-fold universe [1-188], gravity emerges from entanglement through the multi-fold mechanisms. As a result, gravity-like effects appear in between entangled particles [1,24,25], whether they are real or virtual. Long range, massless gravity results from entanglement of massless virtual particles [1,26]. Entanglement of massive virtual particles leads to massive gravity contributions at very small scales [1,27]. It is at the base of the E/G Conjecture [24], and the main characteristics of the multi-fold theory [22]. Multi-folds mechanisms also result in a spacetime that is discrete, with a random walk fractal structure and non-commutative geometry [62], in a range of spatial scales, which is Lorentz invariant and where spacetime nodes and particles can be modeled with microscopic black holes [1,4]. All these recover General Relativity (GR) at large scales, and semi-classical model remain valid till smaller scales than usually expected. Gravity can therefore be added to the Standard Model (SM) resulting into what we define as SM_G : the SM with gravity effects non-negligible at its scales. It can contribute to resolving several open issues with the Standard Model, and the standard cosmological model, without New Physics³⁴ other than gravity [1,4-188]. These considerations hint at an even stronger relationship between gravity and the Standard Model, as finally shown in [23]. It leads us to consider that the multi-fold theory gives good insight to conventional Physics, that our real universe may be well modeled as a multi-fold universe [1,4-188], something that we have done in this paper.

Among the multi-fold SM_G discoveries, the apparition of an-always in-flight, and hence non-interacting, right-handed neutrinos, coupled to the Higgs boson, generated by chirality flips by gravity of the massless Weyl fermions, induced by 7D space time matter induction and scattering models, and hidden behind the Higgs boson or field at the entry points and exit points of the multi-folds. Massless Higgs bosons can be modeled as minimal microscopic black holes mark concretized spacetime locations. They can condensate into Dirac Kerr-Newman soliton Qballs to produce massive and charged particles below the energy scales of the multi-fold electroweak symmetry breaking [1,4], and as random walk patterns to realize massless particles at all scales [1,29,36,37], thereby providing a microscopic explanation for a the multi-fold kinematics and dynamics and associated unconstrained Kaluza Klein mechanisms [23,33,34,52,63,64,113,139], Higgs driven inflation [1,27], the electroweak symmetry breaking, the Higgs mechanism, the mass acquisition [139], and the chirality of fermions (and spacetime); all resulting from the multi-fold gravity electroweak symmetry breaking [1,4,17,23,29,32-34,52,64,66,72,74,124,139,140]. The multi-fold theory has concrete implications on New Physics like supersymmetry, superstrings, M-theory and Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) [1,8-21,66,90,112,134].

Multi-folds are encountered in GR at Planck scales [5,6] and in Quantum Mechanics (QM) if different suitable quantum reference frames (QRFs) are to be equivalent relatively to entangled, coherent or correlated systems [7].

³⁴ Conventional physicists may argue it is New Physics. We consider that it isn't because no new particles or interactions are introduced. We just add gravity, as we know it should be, and multi-fold mechanism and let conventional Physics unfold with the considerations. It does change conventional results or explanations, usually with same observables, and it does live in a discrete spacetime etc. as a result of conventional analysis of these consequences. We also do not cover stable field effects like Skyrmions [166], that we prefer to see as a collective effect for the theory. Beside the SM particles, there are other collective solutions/solitons in gauge theories, they have behaviors as particles but they are quasi-particles composed of collective effects of a large set of particles. We see them as Qballs or patterns that can appear by multi-fold space time matter induction and scattering, under specific circumstances, nothing more. They are topological solitons and can appear in BEC, as expected with massless Higgs boson condensates [171,172].

This shows that GR and QM are different facets of something that they cannot well model: multi-folds [1,52,94,104].

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